

PP-20 : Appropriateness of antiplatelet prescriptions and their unwarranted impact on the institutional pharmaceutical budget in a primary healthcare setting in Sri Lanka

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BACKGROUND:

- Recent guideline updates have refined the indications for antiplatelet therapy to optimise patient care.
- Inappropriate prescriptions of antiplatelets are a health risk for patients and cause unnecessary financial burden on the healthcare system.

OBJECTIVE:

- To assess the **appropriateness** of antiplatelet prescriptions and their **unwarranted impact** on the institutional **pharmaceutical budget** in a primary healthcare setting in Sri Lanka.

METHODS:

- A descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted in the outpatient medical clinic of a primary medical care unit (PMCU) in Sri Lanka.
- Records of all patients followed up from **January to December 2023** were evaluated.
- Records of patients lost to follow up, deceased and transferred/discharged from the clinic during the study period were excluded.
- Data extraction sheets were used to extract data from patient records, annual pharmaceutical estimate, stock transfer vouchers and drug stores register.
- The **2019 American Heart Association / American College of Cardiology guidelines** was used as the reference.

RESULTS:

- Sixty one out of 234 clinic patients were on antiplatelet therapy of which **80% were females**. Median age was 74 years and **90% were ≥65 years**. (**Table 2**)
- Most (60.7%) were on antiplatelets for secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease.
- A **57.4%** was on **inappropriate prescriptions**, mainly for primary prevention (68.6%) (**Table 3**).
- The price of an aspirin tablet was Rs 1.234 and a clopidogrel tablet was Rs 3.4 for 2023.
- Nearly **53% of the budget allocated** for antiplatelets was spent on **inappropriate prescriptions**. (i.e., Rs 23219.84 from Rs 43837.96)

Table 1: List of Guidelines on antiplatelet therapy 2012-2019

Year	Guideline
2012	ACCP guidelines
2015	AHA/ADA scientific statement
2016	ADA guidelines
2016	USPSTF recommendation statement
2019	AHA/ACC guidelines
2022	USPSTF recommendation statement

Table 2: Prevalence of risk factors for bleeding among the patients on antiplatelet therapy (n=61)

Risk factors identified	n (%)
Age ≥ 65years	55 (90.2)
Sex (female)	49 (80.3)
Diabetes	33 (54.1)
Hypertension	58 (95.1)
Polypharmacy	49 (80.3)
Multimorbidity	60 (98.4%)
Low body mass index	in 43 (6/43 – 14.0%)

Table 3: Prevalence of risk factors for bleeding among the patients on antiplatelet therapy (n =61)

Antiplatelet prescription	Reason	n (%)
Appropriate		26 (42.6)
Inappropriate		35 (57.4)
Monotherapy	Primary prevention	24/35 (68.6)
	Candidate for dual antiplatelets	1/35 (2.9)
Dual therapy	More than recommended duration	10/35 (28.6)

CONCLUSION:

- Gaps in translating guidelines to practice and lack of medication review may have caused inappropriate prescription of antiplatelet agents placing patients at undue health risks while posing a financial risk to the healthcare system.

KEY HIGHLIGHTS:

- Two-fold public risk: health and finance
- The two-fold burden on state healthcare
- The need for structured medication review
- The need to keep up with the guidelines